

The Skill of Writers in Using Graphic Devices

Haydarov Anvar Askarovich ¹, Sattorova Shakhrizoda ²

¹ Professor of the Department of English Linguistics of Bukhara State University

² 2nd year master's degree student

Annotation:

In this article, the skill of using phonographic stylistic devices in the works of English and Uzbek poets and writers is analyzed, besides, the stylistic features expressed in them are highlighted on the basis of examples.

Keywords: phonostylistics, graphic stylistics, phonography, artistic text, ellipsis, symbolic synonymy, allusion, contrast, anaphora, alliteration, rhyme, epiphora, phonics.

Introduction. Phonopoetic devices used in the literary work in accordance with the content and rhythm of the poem have a strong impact on the reader's feelings. Since the main element of a literary work is the word, language in general, its language and the author's ability to use language devices and the extent which the author can use language devices are the main factors in making to the level of art.

Essence. Studying the language of the works of writers who have a great impact in our literature, first of all, comes from the need to study the skill of the writer, at the same time, to determine the impact of the language of his works on the development of our language, and the extent which the research affects the development of our linguistics. When talking about the phonetics of a literary work, the time and place of its writing, language features specific to that place and time, numbers and variants of sounds, phonetic rules, sound pairs and other features, from which language it is taken or the sound of its own layer, syllable position, tonal aspects are of great prominence.

Literature review. Writers and poets who effectively used various phonographic devices in their works, first of all, aimed to understand the written speech for each language, convey the idea to others in an understandable way, and convey the meaning to the listener exactly as the writer wanted. Examples of the works of Uzbek notable writers and poets: A.Navoi, A.Cholpon, H.Khudoyberdiyeva, A.Mukhtar, A.Kadiri, P.Kadirov, Sh.Kholmirezayev, S.Ahmad; from English

writers E.Dickinson, T.S.Eliot, W.Faulkner, M.Shelley, M.Herron, E.Ch.Jones, J.D.Salinger, S.McCarthy, T.Morrison are included and their analysis is discussed in detail.

Analysis and results. We know that linguistics and literary studies are closely related to one another. They are regarded as mutually reinforcing sectors. Linguopoetics is a shortened form of linguistic poetics, which studies the artistic-aesthetic functions of linguistic units (phonetic, lexical, morphological) used in a literary work, and the emotional-expressive function of language. In the process of analyzing literary texts, it is necessary to pay special attention to the aesthetic properties of phonetic units. In the poetic texts, the artistic and aesthetic possibilities of speech sounds are perceived quickly and easily. Because the poem has a unique attractive tone. This melodiousness is achieved as a result of stylistically unusual use of sounds. Poetic texts mainly use phonetic stylistic devices such as alliteration (repetition of consonants), assonance (repeat of vowels), gemination (layering of consonants). In prose, expressiveness is provided by phonetic devices such as lengthening vowels, folding consonants, repeating sounds, mispronouncing words, adding sounds or dropping sounds. The poetic use of speech sounds (exactly) consonants in the literary text also occurs as a result of their repetition. Among the phonopoetic devices that serve to ensure the melodiousness and effectiveness of figurative speech, the role of the repetition of such sounds is incomparable. I.B. Golub, in his work entitled "Stylistics of the Russian language of modern times", while discussing the phonetic level of linguistics, distinguishes phonics and phonostylistics from each other. "Also, phonics means the phonetic organization of speech, that is, the selection and use of language devices at the phonetic level for a certain stylistic purpose. "Phonics" means devices of stylistic importance at the phonetic level of the language"[1]. The linguist scientist S. Karimov, who has deeply studied the field of phonostylistics in Uzbek linguistics, notes that as a result of his research, phonics and phonostylistics have certain differences from the point of view of the object of study. A linguist scientist, "phonostylistics in general studies the aspects of the phonetic formation of speech with certain stylistic goals, as well as the functional-stylistic differentiation of speech sounds, i.e., inter-stylistic characteristics and features of use, while phonics studies rhythm, alliteration, sound imitation, rhyme, assonance, and even non-standard pronunciations made to create laughter or satirical effectiveness, that consists poetic and prosaic texts from the point of view of sound[2].

Phonographic devices are expressive means used to express emotions in written form through intonation and stress in oral speech. Expressing the state of spirituality in literary works creates a unique complexity. In representing the exact meaning of internal excitement in the spirit of the characters, happiness, sadness, approval, surprise, begging, irony, pity, applause, questioning, emphasis, dissatisfaction, protest, desire, support - writers use the method of writing vowels or consonants more than one in their works. By writing vowels and consonants more than once, meanings such as prolonged pronunciation, surprise, excitement, excess of signs, and strength of duration are understood. For example,

Weakness of the sign: *Ortiq jizzaki ko 'rinmaslik uchun bos-i-iq tovush bilan dedi...* (P. Kadirov).

Predominance of the sign: *Uzo-oq yo 'l, ahyo-onda bir keladi, qato-or imoratlar, o 'yla-ab tursam, o 'g 'lim, dunyoni ishi qiziq.* (A. Mukhtar)

-A-a-a, o 'sha sizmidingiz, buni qarang-a, tanimapman. Uyimizga yana bir kelgan ekansiz. Yo 'qligimni qarang-a. (S. Ahmad)

Men o 'zimning odmi plashimni ham devordan daromad qiiib yasalgan shifonerga ildim. - O-o! - deb yana o 'zi ichkariga yo 'l tortdi Tavakkal -Yaxshi-ii... A, Gulsara? Bir kishiga bo 'ladi-da! (Sh. Kholmirezayev)

Excess of sign: *Siz aslida uchchiga chiqqan muttaham ekansiz!* (From the newspaper).

The instant of movement: *Salimani ko 'rishi bilan Ziynat xola zippilab ko 'zdan g 'oyib bo 'ldi.*

The high pitch of voice: *"Bummm" degan tovush eshitildi-yu, ko 'kni chang- to 'zon qopladi.*

The duration of the movement: *Yarim soatlik qonli "g'ov-v-v-v, g'u-v-v-v, ov-v-v-v-v, ov-v-v-v»dan so 'ng Mallaxonning davangisi mag 'lub bo 'lib, faje bir suratda yaralandi. (A.Kadiri) .*

Graphon is a device used to individualize the character's speech in a literary work and to bring the expression closer to oral - live speech. In some places, words are deliberately distorted and written in such a way as to cause laughter. For example:

-Kotibadan, kirsam mumkinmi, deb so 'rash kerak. -Jinni bo 'ldingmi, Ne'mat? -Men sizga Ne'mat emasman, o 'rtoq Babbayev bo 'laman, o 'rtoq Xajjayip. (S.Ahmad)

-Xo 'p, bo 'pti. Uning oti Zulfiqor, fomilasi... -aytaveraymi, deb unga qaradi. (S.Ahmad).

Alliteration. Alliteration is the repeated use of the same consonants at the beginning or end of syllables in verses and words in poetic speech [3]. Alliteration adds smoothness, pleasantness, positive attitude, intonation integrity to the content of artistic works and gives it sonority.

"So we beat on, boats against the current, borne back ceaselessly into the past."

"I give you the mausoleum of all hope and desire; I give it to you not that you may remember time, but that you might forget it now and then." (W. Faulkner)

Anaphore, a word or a combination of words is repeated at the beginning of the verses. Thinkers of the ancient world believed that always starting a sentence with the same word adds charm to the speech, ensures its solemnity and vitality. Therefore, anaphore should be considered not as a decoration or an external sign of speech, but also as a means of strengthening the meaning. Anaphora uses the same repetitive constructions at the beginning of a line, paragraph, and sentence. These can be in the form of a word, a phrase, a sentence. For example:

Birga tug 'ilmoq bor, birga turmoq yo 'q.

Qaysi bir ozorin aytay jononima ag 'yorning,

Qaysi bir og 'ritganin ko 'nglimni dey dildorning (Z.M.Bobur).

"When he woke in the woods in the dark of the night and he was cold... when he woke in the woods in the dark of the night..." (C.McCarthy)

"If you want to fly, you have to give up the things that weigh you down." (T.Morrison)

Epiphora is a Latin word, "epi" means "after" and "phoros" means meaning. The repetition of vowels or consonants at the end of words, the same construction at the end of verses, sentences, paragraphs is called epiphora [3]. Anaphora is used in spoken and written speech, and epiphora is mainly used in written speech:

Bunda bor: harorat, muhabbat, shafqat va mehnat nonini ko 'ramiz baham. (Gafur Gulam)

"I hope she'll be a fool—that's the best thing a girl can be in this world, a beautiful little fool." (F.S. Fitzgerald)

Conclusion. Graphic changes not only reflect the specific features of pronunciation, but are also used to highlight stressed words and express the intensity of emphasis. The use of phonetic devices in speech for the purpose of performing a stylistic task is a product of necessity arising from art in general, as well as from the creative skills of a poet or writer. That is, subordinating language units to serve an artistic-aesthetic purpose of these tools, and thus characterizing some of them to an artistic style further strengthens their place in this style.

REFERENCES:

1. Golub I.B. Stylistics of the modern Russian language. - M.: "Higher School", 1986.- P.259-260.)
2. Karimov S. O'zbek tilining fonetik stilistikasi. –Samarqand, 2016.- B.15.
3. A.Hojiyev. Lingvistik belgilarning izohli lug'ati, - T: 1985.- B.30.
4. Yaxshiyeva G. O'zbek tilida fonografik uslubiy vositalar. – T., "Fan" nashriyoti.1996.-36b.
5. Yo'ldoshev M. Badiiy matn va uning lingvopoetik tahlili asoslari.- T: Fan, 2010.
6. Haydarov A.A. Yozuv bilan bog'liq uslubiy xususiyatlar.(ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari to'plami).-Buxoro: 2020.- B.19-22.(Haydarov A.A. Methodological features related to writing. (a collection of scientific and practical conference materials).- Bukhara: 2020.- P.19-22
7. Хайдаров А.А. Коннотатив маънонинг фонетик воситаларда ифодаланиши: филол. фан. номз. дисс. – Т., 2009. – Б. 14
8. Askarovich, H. A. (2021). EXPRESSION OF CONNOTATIVE MEANING IN GRAPHIC MEANS. *International Engineering Journal For Research & Development*, 6 (TITFL), 91–94.
9. Haydarov, A. A. (2019). METHODOLOGICAL FEATURES OF IMITATION WORDS. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (10), 688-690.
https://www.elibrary.ru/ip_restricted.asp?rpage=https%3A%2F%2Fwww%2Eelibrary%2Eru%2Fitem%2Easp%3Fid%3D41328966.
10. Askarovich, H. A. (2021). EXPRESSION OF CONNOTATIVE MEANING IN GRAPHIC MEANS. *International Engineering Journal For Research & Development*, 6, 91-94.
11. Haydarov, A. (2020). Methodological features of graphic tools. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 5.
12. Askarovich, H. A. (2022). SOME COMMENTS ON THE STYLISTIC REPETITION. *JournalNX-A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal*, 8 (1), 87–91.
13. Haydarov, A. (2019). Madaniyat va san'at sohasini boshqarish asoslari. O'quv qo'llanma. *Toshkent. - "Kamalak" nashriyoti*, 192.
14. Askarovich, H. A. (2023). THE PROBLEM OF THE STUDY OF ANTHROPONYMS. *Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*, 11(3), 868-870.
15. Haydarov, A. A. (2023). KOMBINATOR VA POZITSION FONETIK O'ZGARISHLARNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI (INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARI MISOLIDA). *SUSTAINABILITY OF EDUCATION, SOCIO-ECONOMIC SCIENCE THEORY*, 1(6), 172-175.
16. Navruzova, N., & Haydarov, A. (2021). CONNOTATIVE MEANINGS RELATED TO SOUND CHANGES. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 8(8).
http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/4462.
17. Askarovich, H. A. (2021). Alliteration and Assonance in Artistic Image-As a Stylistic Figure. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH AND INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES* (Vol. 2, pp. 114-119).
18. Haydarov, A. A., & Mansurova, D. (2023). THE ROLE OF INTONATION IN SPEECH AND ARTISTIC SPEECH. *Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*, 11(1), 673-676.

19. Askarovich, H. A. (2023). THE EXPRESSION OF THE INTENSITY OF WORDS AT LANGUAGE LEVELS. *Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*, 11(1), 638-642.
20. A. A. Haydarov, & M. Yunusova. (2022). THE PHENOMENON OF POLYSEMY. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 2044–2048. Retrieved from <https://www.giirj.com/index.php/giirj/article/view/4251>